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Racism in Japan : Critical Analysis on Japan's Xenophobia and Racial Discrimination

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Abstract:

Racism in Japan is a topic that has received scant academic attention. Racism has had a big effect on the way people interact in Japan. But the existing literature doesn't conclude enough about how racism really looked during different era and situation in Japan and how it affected people. Using the document analysis method, this research looks at how racism affects minorities and foreigners in Japan. It appears to look at the government's position and the point of view of Japanese society, examines old and new data, and tries to have a basic understanding of Japanology, sociology, and psychology. This research shows that racism has serious effects on the economy, job, promotion, housing problems, social behavior, and other things for Japanese minorities and foreigners.

Keywords: Japanese Racism, Black people, Race relations, Hate speech, Imperialism, Housing issue in Japan, Being Japanese, Xenophobia in Japan, Work in Japan, Zainichi Koreans, Foreigners in Japan, Homogenous society.

1. Introduction:

Racism is the idea that people can be separated into groups called "races" that are different from each other (Wilson, 1987). This word is also used for political, economic, or legal institutions that discriminate based on race or keep it going. It means the idea that some races are better by nature than others. According to the 2006 UN Report on racism, racial discrimination, xenophobia, and other kinds of discrimination, 98.45% of the country's 127.7 million inhabitants are Japanese citizens. This comprises the native Ainu and the 1.5% outsiders (Commission of Human Rights, 2006). This report looked into racism and hostility towards foreigners exist in Japan or not and got by investigation that they do. This report says that minority population in Japan are left out of society and ignored by the government. They also say that there are existence traditional, cultural and historical elements which are ignored though these factors lead to racial discrimination. In 2014, the UN said, "There is still a lot of racism in Japan, and the government doesn't see how bad

the problem is" (Brincrest & Gannon, 2014). They also talk about how the Japanese government and media don't recognize much about racism and racial issues of Japan. The Japan Times Herald mentioned that after the UN research on Japan's racism came out, there was no news or report in Japanese media. The Japanese government, on the other hand, says that racism has no existence in Japan. The reason is the ICERD does not include Japan's minority population in its definition of "race" according to the government (Maeda, 2010). The government says that racism doesn't exist in Japan, but the committee says that Japan needs to admit that it does and Japan has to define "race" and "racism" in constitution. Again, they wanted the government to make laws, rules in order to stop discrimination and to punish those who do it (The committee, 2014). From the different things the Japanese Government and the UN have said about race and racism, this is clear, there is a no doubt lacks of understanding or misrecognition of definition of race. Even though the country supported the ICERD officially during the year, 1995, This might be claimed that this doesn't help until they don't fully recognize the existence of racism in Japan. This problem is harder to solve as the government doesn't have a clear idea about what race is as well as doesn't agree that racism exists in Japan. Racism in Japan now entails addressing Japan's colonial heritage and the immigration enforcement system that deems all ethnic minorities, including those born after the conquest, as foreigners (Parx, 2017). Far-right organizations, notably Zaitokukai, were branded "alt-right" as they promoted racist beliefs online and harmed individuals in Japan (Lwabauch & Takezawa, 2015). In the last few years, racism started to show up in Japan's big cities. Academics and activist groups whom got worried of the rise of racial discrimination in Japan have started protests and movements to fight it (Morris & Suzuki, 2015). Most people talk about this problem in terms of the rights of foreigners in Japan (Shibuichi, 2016). It only suggests that the minority group is in Japan for a short time.

2. Literature review:

There are many things that lead to racism in Japan. The way racism is hidden in modern Japan has to do with how Japanese think about race and how Japanese see themselves (Kaiwai, 2015). Several pieces of writing have shown that the western idea of racism has influenced the Japanese idea of racism (Morris-Suzuki ,2000). Miles said in 1993 that racism in the west happens in six steps. Firstly, to bring people closer together, either physically (through labor migration) or in the way they talk to each other (through the official promotion of a group or tribe of "outsiders" beyond the established borders of the nation-state). During the Meiji period, Japan had rules that made it clear who was a "insider" and who was a "outsider" (Gannon, 2014). For example, Japan used slogans in its new national story to make people aware that there were "Others," even physically different "Others," far away from the next village (The Hindu, 2018). Secondly, to make differences between these people based on where they are from, what language they speak, how they look, etc., and back them up with laws and made-up traditions. Japan did the same thing. Even though Japan was an empire that encouraged Asian people to be friends, it was still clear who was a "Japanese," who was a "colonist," and who was a "foreigner" (Asano, 1993). Thirdly, to say that these differences are normal because they are based on blood or ideas. Japan still does this, as

shown by the fact that you have to have Japanese blood to become a citizen (Weiner, 2009). Also, culture and ideology still play a role in how Japanese public policy and social science deal with "different" people. Fourth, thought that these differences were bad. Volumes of pre-imperial and post-imperial scholarship, as well as the postwar nativist discourse of Nihonjinron (theories of Japanese uniqueness in cultural and national identity), have been written about how Japan's tropes of difference and uniqueness mean that it is better than the "Other" (Ameda, 2000). Fifthly, to think that "the Other" can't be part of the national body. Lastly, to say that the "Other" is a threat to the national order just by being there. Japan has done a great job with this. As we'll see in later chapters, slogans and policies from the Meiji Era made it clear that "Others" from other countries needed to be kept away from Japanese people, who were citizens of the nation-state (Itano, 2013). During the Meiji Era, foreign scholars and advisors could only work in Japan for short amounts of time (Higuchi, 1985). Japan was able to get rid of its empire after World War II because it had control over its colonies. During the Bubble Era, Japan's "internationalization" (Kokusaika) policies still kept "outsiders" from voting (Paku, 2002), and even today's visa rules keep foreign and migrant labor in a "revolving door" status, which is justified by the official claim that foreigners are a threat to Japan's social order (Gannon, 2014). People say that Japan doesn't have racism. But this literature review takes a close look at current books, articles, and interviews that show racism exists in Japan. As an example, a 2016 survey by Japan's justice ministry found that 40% of foreigners, most of whom were Chinese and Korean, had housing problems and that 1 in 5 thought they were paid less than Japanese people for the same work (The Hindu, 2017). People in Japan today just think of themselves as Nihonjin, and racism is seen as an issue outside of Japan (Kaiwai,2020). Different parts of Japanese history are used to build up the idea of racism (Arudou,2021). In fact, racism in modern Japan has something to do with the idea of Japaneseness (Tsuda ,2022). The way racism is done in Japan now is different from how it is done in other parts of the world (Kearney ,1994). People usually think of Japan as a country where everyone is the same. But racism in Japan looks at how Japaneseness was made from the point of view of a country in transition (Koshiro ,1992).

3. Gaps:

A number of gaps can be identified in the existing literature. The reviewed literature doesn't provide solid and sufficient information to explain reasons of Xenophobia in Japan. It also fails to explain Government of Japan's perspective on racism clearly after surveys conducted in 2016 and the absence of anti-discrimination legislation and NHRI in Japan. The present literature explains there is racism because of ethnicity but doesn't divide particular racism towards particular race, as for example how is an American being treated or a Chinese being treated in Japan. Same for sex, present literature doesn't show different behaviors towards male and female. There is lacks of information about how sexual minorities are being treated in Japan, facing discrimination or not and particular behaviors towards black people. There is no information of what Japanese people think of their own behaviors and racism, what they feel. There is literature about racism in Japan during Covid-19, but after Covid-19 there is lacks of information to explain context.

4. Objectives:

As a result, this research strives to help minimize the gaps in the current literature. This research seeks to achieve its general objectives by focusing on the following specific topics:

1. To find out reason for not having any law and NHRI against racism in Japan explaining government's perspective.
2. To explain forms of racism, mediums and reasons of Xenophobia and discrimination in Japan from existing literature and surveys.
3. To explain myth of Nihonjiron and relate ethnicity and racism and will try to give a hair-spitting discussion about racism towards different races and genders².
4. To discuss Japanese behavior towards black people and people having tattoos and adopting western cultures.
5. To discuss foreigners, sufferers and Japanese perspective on racism.
6. Analysis of racism under Covid-19 in Japan and how is situation afterwards

5. Research questions:

As a consequence of prior literature research, this study will provide answers to following questions:

Research Question:1

What is the real aspect of Racism in Japan and what are the factors still keeping Xenophobia alive in Japan?

Research Question:2

How is ethnicity related to racism in Japan and how is life of black people and in Japan? How was racism under Covid-19 in Japan and how is situation afterwards?

6. Methodology:

To get information for this study, a document analysis method and a web-surfing data collection method are used. The technique of thematic data analysis is used to look at data and come up with themes. Most of the findings for this discussion comes from documents, journals, books, e-books, YouTube reviews, case studies, blogs, web surfing, research papers, etc. Very recently published online data is used to address the research question. It works by getting information from trusted websites and sources like NHK, The Japan Times, Tofugu, Bunraku, etc. There is both thematic and analytical information in this paper. Ethics were taken very seriously in the study, and the data sources were checked to ensure the results to be real and authentic. To improved clarity and better understandings of the readers, several interviews conducted by authentic sources sometimes

directly quoted in the analytical section of this study. Finally, at the end of the paper, credit was given to each piece of information that made this paper better.

7. Limitations of the Study and Scope of Future Research:

This study examines the impact of racism on different minorities and foreigners in Japan with a particular emphasis on forms of racism in Japan, Xenophobia, government laws, psychology of Japanese people on racism and other aspects of racism and society in Japan that have been excluded from the prerogative of this study. However, the study encourages future research on racial discrimination, gender discrimination, behavioral changes and conflict in the Covid-19 context. Moreover, only secondary data have been used for this study. In addition, the study is less robust due to the use of secondary data; primary sources would have been preferable.

8. Analysis and findings:

8.1 'Nihonjiron': 'Non-racist' racism in Japan

Japan had a population of 127.7 million people, of whom 98.45% are Japanese citizens, according to the UN Report (Commission of Human Right, 2006). This contains the Ainu, a single indigenous group, and foreigners, who make up only 1.55% of the total population. The reporter looked into the existence of racial discrimination and xenophobia in Japan, also discovered, they do exist. This report claims all minority population in Japan face social marginalization, political neglect, and significant cultural and historical aspects that, while overlooked, really contribute to discriminatory practices. According to a UN study from 2014, racism is still pervasive in Japan and the administration is unaware of its depth (Brincrest and Gannon, 2014). They also make reference to the media and government of Japan's ignorance of the country's systemic racism. After the UN issued its report on Japan. After that The Japan Times reported, no reports or news appeared in Japanese media. The Japanese government, on the other hand, is confident that racism is not prevalent in Japan. Since the minority groups in Japan do not match the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination's concept of "race" (Maeda, 2010). The committee stresses government to acknowledge the issue and identify "race" and racism inside the Japanese Constitution, in opposition to the government's assertion that they deny racism exists in Japan. They also urge that the government of Japan enact legal framework to outlaw and protect minorities there (The committee, 2014). It is clear that there is a twisted view or representation of race based on the clear distinctions in the statements given by the Japanese Government and the UN about race and racism. Although Japan agreed and signed the ICERD at late twentieth century, that might be stated that this didn't make circumstances any better since Japan persists to not truly recognize the presence of racism in the country. Because the government lacks a concept of race and denies the existence of racism in Japan, this issue became more tough to solve. This is important to comprehend "Nihonjinron (Japan's concept)," which is generally

acknowledged notion that Japan is a homogenous nation, to close the comprehension gap regarding race and racism. People claim that Japan's population is culturally and ethnically homogenous. Because there are no minority groups in Japan, so in their opinion, racism has no chance to create existence there. This idea forms the foundation for the Japanese government's rejection of racism. It may be claimed that the most crucial method to discuss racism in Japan is to comprehend and rectify "Nihonjinron." So, it is important to see how it has developed through time, how well this concept results to "not-racist" racism in Japan, and exactly what it would mean being a Japanese.

Racism did exist before Japan came across the idea of race and racial discrimination, what the Government of Japan denies, in form of the incursion of the north or "Buraku" discrimination in Japan. This is therefore challenging to claim, Japan has always been culturally and ethnically homogenous. The "Nihonjinron," or Imperial system founded on mythology, group-based culture, and solidarity, was steadily established in societal structure till Japan experienced modernization in the middle of the nineteenth century. Although there are no recognized ethnic minorities in Japan, the history of the nation is closely tied to immigrants from mainland Asia, according to a 1989 assessment by the Japanese government. A Chinese group was formally allowed by the government during the Edo period, and there are records of migratory labourers from the ancient age (Asano, 1993). Furthermore, Japan's establishment as a nation with all of its current provinces and territories is a very recent development (Ishiro, 2002). For example, Okinawa and Hokkaido were joined in the late nineteenth century, and the old country that was centered on the south half did not include the Tohoku area, in the north. This suggests that civilizations in various locations should be cultural variety. Japan has several cultures and ethnic groups throughout the preceding decades, hence it cannot be argued that it is a homogenous state. It doesn't mean Japan to be multi-cultural or multi-racial, because racism has always been there, even though people do not employ the word "racism". As a result of the caste-like system that positioned the lowly people known as *Eta / Hinin* in lowest position of hierarchy during feudal period of the Edo Period, discrimination against "Buraku" people was alleged to have begun (the committee, 2006). Because racism in Japan doesn't match the notion of race, which the country defines as biological characteristics like skin tone, so the government doesn't recognize the presence of racism (Maeda, 2010). Therefore, "Buraku" discrimination represents racism since it targets individuals according to their social status, cultural identity, and ancestry, which at the time was seen as distinct. This discrimination adheres to the modern concept of racism (Law, 2010). Asano (1993) states the notion of "nation" and "nationals" as Japan and Japanese originated in nineteenth century, therefore before then, there hadn't been any clear thought on Japan's race. Paku (2002) argues a king has always been a crucial figure in Japanese culture and identity. The sixth-century book "Kojiki" describes Japan as a land in which the emperors, who are descended directly from the deity (Amaterasu), reign over the people who are likewise descended directly from the deity. As a result, everyone in Japan under the emperor is seen as belonging to a single kinship ties and race. It might be argued at this stage that Japan had already begun to racialize itself as a distinct race from others. A core characteristic of Japan, known as "Nihonjinron," existed prior to modernization and the

formation of nationalism, in contrast toward systemic racialization. Ruth Benedict claims that "group-orientation" and "embarrassment" cultures are the foundation of Japanese civilization. Because of how oppressed the Japanese people are by this belief, these aspects of Japanese society promote cultural and ethnic uniformity. Racial discrimination was so present in Japan before World War II. Furthermore, despite the notion of uniformity, Japan has never been a nation with a single race, civilization, or ethnic background. The nation has historically been home to a wide variety of cultures and ethnic groups. But as some historians still believe, mythological and traditional elements in the pre-modern time supported the notion that Japan was a homogenous nation from the beginning. And Today's society is still influenced by it. Under the influence of imperialism, Japan defined the concept significantly throughout the post-modern era. This encouraged Japan to become more militaristic and send armies to other countries in Asia.

Japan has racism despite the government's denials. Racist victims in Japan don't match the Constitution's concept of race. In the larger concept of race, the Ainu and Buraku people constitute a separate lineage. This is racial discrimination to this people. Government and society should immediately acknowledge racism's presence. "Nihonjinron" mainly causes racism. Pre-war Japan had a variant of the emperor system centered upon mythology and a group-based, collectivistic society. Before the notion of single nation state, they have had the distinctive idea of "Japanese" and "others." The Meiji Restoration reflected the nation's idea. European nations taught them how to fight invasion. They feared for the nation. To prove the supremacy of Japan's race, a new concept of race based on physical traits, eugenics, and scientific racism were devised. Japanese were meant to be part of the "yellow" race, but they protested the inferiority and created "Nihonjinron." They highlighted Japan's race and difference from other Asian people, leading to imperialism. It emphasized racial supremacy, which led to invasions and massacres of Asians. As imperialism ended in 1945, nationalism diminished, but it stayed in the form of "Nihonjinron." In late twentieth "new-nationalism" movements stressed on Japan's uniformity centered upon the emperor/ Shido. "Nihonjinron" is one of the major causes of racism in Japan as well as it is the main reason behind the government's rejection on racism exists in Japan. Mixed-blood persons are seldom discriminated. The issue is severe. They're viewed as outsiders due to their looks. Also, "others" prejudices or unfavorable attributions may lead to bullying or mistreatment. Being Japanese is incredibly difficult. They must be of "Japanese race," have at least one Japanese parent, share the culture, seem Japanese, etc. Moreover, no one can completely articulate what it means to be Japanese and what they require since the term is unclear in Japan. The individual's judgment determines identity. Nihonjinron's persecution prevents individuals from calling oneself "Japanese." So, this theory, "Nihonjinron" causes racism in Japan. The myth persisted throughout history and still impacts Japanese ethnicity, identity, and hostile attitudes toward immigrants. Changing rules or fighting prejudice would have failed without this idea. The Japanese government and people must realize that the "myth" was socially and historically established to unify and dominate the nation in the past. They must transcend their self-image.

8.2 Japan's Modernization: Meeting Western Racism

In Japan, the Western concept of race had a significant impact. In order to prevent invasion by European nations, the Japanese government was frantic to industrialize and modernize the nation, therefore they sought advice from them on how to accomplish it. As a result of being introduced to new concepts of culture and race at that time, Japan experienced a significant shift. People had experienced the concept of race that is defined by physical characteristics like skin tone, and had established eugenics and socio-darwinism simultaneously. They created their own unique type of racialization and racial group categories inside the nation in order to safeguard its sovereign rights and also to defend its incursion of land and discrimination against the other Asian nations under imperialism. This was done by combining new and pre-modern racial knowledge. In 1868, the Meiji Restoration transformed the government's structure. Because of the need to strengthen the nation in order to prevent colonization by European nations, this restoration took place. Several Japanese academics were sent overseas at this time. In an effort to modernize Japan in the same way as other nations, they had studied the governance, sociology, economics and literature in Europe then returned to Japan with their findings. As a result, they made significant attempts throughout this time to adopt culture of Western civilization and science, so the West had a significant impact on them. As a result, it is a crucial moment when people experienced the notion of "race" in a European setting, which even the government of Japan currently claims as a justification for their idea of racism. Some academics introduced this new conception of race to Japan, which was distinct from what Japan had held in the years before to the war (Weiner, 2009). They had never before encountered the concept of race, that was mostly centered on a person's physical characteristics. This was due to the fact that those scholars saw racial, ethnic, and cultural variety during studying in Europe, as well as the fact that Japan began trading freely with many other countries. One of the most well-known Japanese intellectuals of the enlightenment, Yukichi Fukuzawa, is a pivotal figure during this period. He traveled extensively around Europe, Hong Kong, and the United States when he resided during Meiji era. People read a lot of his books and reports on these nations. He published works on how to advance civilization and make the nation greater (Higuchi, 1985). In his work, he described five separate racial groups: yellow, white, black, brown, and red. He claims that each race has its own characteristics, with white being thought to be intellectual, yellow being ambitious, red being combative, black being lazy, and brown being chaotic (Lin, 2011). The Japanese people, who belong to the yellow race, should be able to reach the similar level of growth as Europeans, according to these straightforward and conventional attributions made in his writings. During this time, the concept of races was introduced to Japan and is still prevalent in modern culture. Japan, on the other hand, refused to recognize this racial classification as it was presented. Japanese people are considered to be a member of the yellow race, along with many other Asian people, according to this hypothesis of five separate races. However, in imperial Japan, individuals made an effort to distinguish the Japanese people from many other groups that also belonged to yellow race. Anthropology was promoted during the time in order to demonstrate Japan's unique cultural and racial potential as a nation and to research Japan's beginnings (Itano, 2013). Eugenism was able to demonstrate "purity" of Japan and

supremacy to other Asian populations in conjunction with ethnographic data. We may assume that Fukuzawa was among the philosophers who developed this concept. He advocated birth control and marital regulation, for instance, in his works to develop the nation and advance the race (Ameda, 2000). His eugenics also had socio-darwinism as its foundation. He described the three stages of "civilization": undeveloped, developing, and civilization (Lin, 2011). And since Japanese people are as advanced as Europeans, he thought it should be feasible for Japan to achieve "civilization". Racialism, which grew during this time, contributed to Imperial Japan's development of a eugenic concept and its reason for invading other Asian nations. Those investigations intended to demonstrate Japan's racial superiority. A professor at Kyoto University, a highly regarded academic institution in Japan, produced a study on human physical traits and race relationships in 1924, before Japan entered into war (Miyamoto, 1924). He described his effort as a scientific study that shows the supremacy of Japanese people. In the paper, he compares the brain volume and size of individuals from various ethnic groups in Japan, including the Ainu, Okinawans, Koreans, and Chinese. This comparison reveals that the Japanese race is physiologically superior to others since Japanese people's brains vary in size and quality based on where they come from. Additionally, he talks about the "purity" of the Japanese people, which is also a strength for the nation. As a result, scientific racism, what encouraged the notion of eugenism, was in fact prevalent in Japan, particularly during war, as well as being formally examined by important institutions. According to Shimazono (1995), at this time, imperialism rose to prominence thanks to the pre-modern perception of Japan under the authority of the emperor as a nation "where the god's direct descendant, Japanese emperor ruled." According to Ishiro (2002), this philosophy was as harsh against the nation's citizens as it was toward the trend toward assimilation among Imperial Japan's old colonies. Japan's modernization through Meiji Restoration began in 1868. Confrontation between government and people along with a new racial notion, that were rooted in biological characteristics whereas they had previously racialized individuals based on bloodline. Additionally, they created the new eugenics with the scientific racism to give an effort to demonstrate their superiority biologically over the other Asian groups and to catch up the European culture Socio-Darwinism supported the racist belief that there exist underdeveloped and developed individuals inside the universe, as well as the developed should rule and help the underdeveloped. One of the main causes of Imperial Japan's wartime motivation was this philosophy. By merging racialization and eugenics, they produced a powerful, extreme right nationalistic attitude, which led Japan to engage in external and internal power conflict.

8.3 "New Nationalism" and Racism in Japanese Society

Japanese nationalism nevertheless persists in society as the concept of racial and cultural homogeneity in Japan, despite the fact that it looked to have vanished in 1945 with the end of imperialism. During imperial era, this illusion of homogeneous society served as the foundation for Japanese nationalism, which mistreated Japanese nationals in order to keep power over them under the idea of homogeneity and attempted to integrate "other races," mostly in old colonies (Asano, 1993). According to Shimazono (1995), this concept endured the US-led invasion and

social and political rebuilding to become "Nihonjinron." According to him, much like other nations' faiths, it serves as the foundation for nationhood. This is known as "Nihonjinron" in Japan, because it confuses and leaves a hole in the country's accurate understanding on racism and race. The lack of a clear description of race and racial discrimination in the Japanese constitution and the absence of laws to prohibit and penalize racism serve as proof of Japan's continuing conviction inside its uniformity. This "Nihonjinron" has a problem since they conflate the concepts of race, country, and culture. According to the "Nihonjinron" hypothesis, the term "Japanese" refers to individuals who have a common ancestry and tradition. According to Oblas (1995), the definition of the term "minzoku" as it appears in the English-Japanese secondary school dictionary is "people, race, or country." As Jews are taught to be a "race," this misunderstanding of the notion of race perplexes others and leads people to misuse the term. Asano (1993) further notes that in today's society, the concept of "Nihonjinron," actually functions like a "myth." The issue with this view is that "country" and "ethnicity or race" are often used interchangeably due to their belief that there is just single racial group and culture that everyone in the country shares. Other types of restrictions, like the citizenship system, that grants citizen status on a person's blood line, also exhibit this uncertainty. Additionally, bloodlines and "same" culture serve as an unconscious basis for national identification. Due to faster economic expansion in late twentieth century, a new kind of nationalist idea began to emerge. Thinker Yukio Mishima, for instance, published a book titled "Discussion on the Defense of Culture." In this book, Yukio makes the argument that there needs to be an ultimate ethical standard that every country can agree upon, and that standard should belong to the emperor. Shoichi Saeki also discussed the Shintoism rebirth in Japan in anticipation for the nation's reunification. In contrast hand, several individuals criticized Japan's new nationalistic atmosphere for emerging. According to Shichihei Yamamoto, as it is not universal, what he refers to as "Janism," which is built on the concepts of uniformity and group-based society, must be eradicated. And in modern culture, the notion that Japanese people are physiologically distinct from other races, a kind of scientific racism, remains. The paper of Omoto (1996) on the origins of the Japanese people from standpoint of molecular anthropology contains the evidence. According to him, there are three distinct physiologically separable races: Inu, Japanese and Okinawan. Due to cultural differences, Koreans and Chinese are not included in the term "Japanese people" . He clearly distinguishes between "physical anthropology" and "cultural anthropology," although they are combined, the term "Japanese race" refers to people who can be physiologically classified and possess a distinctive culture and have resided in Japan for a very long period (Omoto, 1996). Thus, "Nihonjinron" continues to be a societal mythology that promotes new nationalism in contemporary Japanese culture and serves as the foundation for the country's rejection of racism.

8.4 Discrimination against “Mixed-blood” and “Being a Japanese”

So, if question arises according to this hypothesis, which racial groups are the targets of racism. The difficulty with racism in Japan that neither the government nor the people identify it as such. Then the next question arises who is harmed by these misunderstandings? The Koreans,

Ainu, Okinawan people and the foreigners are only a few of the minority groups inside Japan who experience discrimination. They are frequently cited as the source for Japan's racism problem, despite the fact that all these groups really aren't considered "racial" minority by the government. In addition to such categories, "mixed-blood" individuals across Japan are still the focus of racism. This kind of discrimination is named as "Xenophobia," but this xenophobia is also a type of racism because this is focused upon the way "Nihonjinron" racializes "others" and "Japan's race." During 2015, it was a heated debate in Japan regarding the subject on what it meant to be "Japanese". One lady was selected to represent Japan in a beauty pageant as Miss Japan. Ariana Miyamoto, who is half Japanese and half African American, received criticism for not being "Japanese" sufficiently. According to Mailonline, many people across the country have shown hostility towards Ariana's championship triumph since they anticipated the honor to be given to a "pure" Japanese lady instead of a "*Hafu*," which means partially Japanese and resembles the derogatory phrase "half-caste" Even though she was born and raised in Japan, communicates in the language well, shares the same lifestyle as other Japanese kids, and has citizenship, she is nonetheless seen as "different" by Japanese people. "Mixed-blood" individuals have historically been stigmatized as belonging to a distinct group and subjected to prejudice (Weiner, 2009). These individuals were so few in numbers that they had little impact on society up to the Edo era (1603–1868) since Japan had minimal contact with other nations. The development of stereotypes or other unfavorable attributes toward them in society was also prevented because of the same reasons. As a result, the class was little researched and was absent from numerous historical situations. But it was clear that they never been given the same treatment as Japanese since at that time, the distinction between "Japanese" and "others" had already been established. Due to the sudden increase in their number and the fact that so many of these people were born into lower socioeconomic classes, the problem with these individuals in the post-war age after 1945 had grown significant (Weiner, 2009). He claims that among minority groups in Japan, this group is the most ignored. This is due to many factors, including the fact they are the sole group to suffer discrimination because of their appearance; the treatment ranges from exclusion from society to inclusion in the society; and the fact that they are, in fact, "Japanese" in the broadest sense. Furthermore, as seen by the continued usage of terms like "mixed-blood" or "*Hafu*," that indicates a half Japanese person, instead of terms like "multi-ethnic," people continue to face prejudice in Japan. As well as a lot of people experience unfair treatment due to misconceptions or derogatory terminology like "others." According to Shibuya and Hagiwara's 2003 research on foreigner stereotypes in Japanese media, a large portion of the population has common misconceptions and unfavorable attitudes about foreigners. They assert that the term "*Gaikokujin* (foreigner)" is accountable for the negative connotations and prejudices. It is founded on the notion that such individuals are distinct from "Japanese," leading to their feelings of hostility or dread. Additionally, while using the term "foreigner," individuals are less likely to perceive the differences between individuals based on their color, culture and ethnicity than to concentrate on how they vary from Japanese people. As a result, the term is often associated with unpleasant emotions. Additionally, they claim that despite the fact that Japanese people today have greater

possibilities to interact with individuals of other races, cultures, and ethnicities, many of them still do not realize the risk of miscommunication. Thus, "mixed-blood" individuals also constitute a target of racism in Japan. The population has not grown to the point where they are ignored, yet while sharing a shared culture, country, and genealogy, they are nevertheless unfairly treated as "others," which causes them to suffer. Therefore, "Nihonjinron" has a very limited definition of what it entails to be a Japanese since it does not acknowledge any distinctions amongst individuals. The sufferers therefore feel excluded from society or mainstream community.

8.5 Racism in Japan: 'Mild Xenophobia' or Reality?

People from across the globe have successfully settled and prospered in Japan, a nation renowned for its hospitable culture. Here the question rises how it is possible for racism to exist here? In a country-wide poll, the Japanese government discovered that about a quarter of foreign immigrants received disparaging comments about their ethnicity. And although some incidents can be better categorized as "mild xenophobia," these are the more upsetting examples of racial intolerance and exclusion that demonstrate what else can arise by uncorrected unfavorable ideas about immigrants. According to a recent survey by the Justice Ministry of Japan, about a 1/3 of foreign citizens in Japan report having encountered disparaging comments due to their race, and around 40% report having experienced discrimination in housing. 4,252 of the 18,500 international respondents that were polled, mostly Korean and Chinese respondents, answered. More than 40% had spent around ten years in Japan. One in five job searchers said they were paid less than their Japanese colleagues for identical work, and one in four claimed that they were rejected recruitment due to being foreigners. The fact that 95% of foreigners whose employment applications were turned down and over 90 percent of the surveyed of those whose housing applications were turned down could speak Japanese "communicatively, skillfully or flawlessly" puts an end to the idea that these discriminations is based on language.

Signs saying "Foreigners Welcome" are often seen outside businesses, from hair salons to bars, in downtown Tokyo's busy neighborhoods. The fact that they are mandated just serves to show that there are certain places in Japan, guest homes, massage parlors, and restaurants, that do not accept foreigners. Some landlords in Japan reject all foreign applications out of hand because they think their renters would prefer not to live with foreigners. One cannot help but ask how much these owners genuinely advocate for their tenants; maybe there is attraction in the idea of a "proper, Japanese-only establishment" "There are various justifications for refusing access to foreigners, from concerns about communication with non-Japanese speakers (despite the fact that so many foreigners speak Japanese) to the idea that foreigners are unprepared for Japanese culture (as like taking off shoes and to speak softly). Some contend that the true intent of these limitations is to prevent big groups of noisy Chinese visitors from "ruining" the environment. The other foreigners are only bystanders.

In Japan, racism often manifests in two ways. Far-right organizations have engaged in violent hate speech directed towards Chinese and Korean people that is based on long-standing historical animosity. Japan has a lengthy history of discriminating against Chinese and Koreans basis of race. Following the Great Kant earthquake during early twentieth century, Japanese vigilante groups slaughtered millions of Koreans and Chinese due to rumors that "Koreans are poisoning the wells" and "Koreans will attack us". Similar "panic" rumors still affect these ethnic communities today, worsened even more by social networking sites. For instance, in 2014, landslides in the Hiroshima Province sparked erroneous reports of ethnic Koreans in Japan known as “Zainichi” breaking into abandoned houses. They appear in ethnic-inspired uniforms outside of school for the children's protection. Those from Japan's old colonies, such as China and Korea and their offspring who were born in Japan, are the primary targets of hateful speech in that country. Japan's leadership has never plead guilty after World War II for the harm it did to other counties it ruled. On the other hand, it employs discriminatory practices against such people, such as daily surveillance, and treats them as if they are aliens without any rights. Hateful remarks and actions against Korean residents of Japan have persisted to this day, coming from both official and private sources. The North Korean president expressed regret for abducting more than ten Japanese people in the 1970s and 1980s during the summit between North Korea and Japan on September 17, 2002. It caused the media and the government to say a lot of derogatory things about Korea, which are still being uttered today. This situation worsened as a result of the rise in hateful speech and racial violence against Koreans, which gave people the impression that they could say anything they wanted about them. In only six months after the meeting in 2002, more than a thousand instances of hate speech and attacks against Korean schoolchildren were documented nationwide. The wearing of the Korean national clothing was prohibited at Korean schools in Japan. Additionally, there is a more widespread discrimination against other immigrants, that is also fueled by uncontested preconceptions. As for example, A train conductor in Osaka apologized publicly to Japanese passengers last year for any "discomfort" caused by the "quantity of foreigners on board". Sometimes, Japanese may prefer travelling by standing instead of sitting beside a foreigner in train (The Hindu, 2021).

8.6 Elaborating Racism: Analyzing Surveys, Interviews and Reports

For the majority of contemporary history, Japan has created a false sense of self-identity called ‘Nihonjinron’ that is spread via literature. The belief that perhaps the nation being homogeneous, religious, racial or ethnic prejudice never could exist in such a location without any variety is at the heart of this delusion. As a result, regulations by the government safeguarding these classes from discrimination were unnecessary. People are now, for the first time, debating what all of this represents inside the historical context and the destiny as number of non-Japanese residents approaches almost two and a half million, or around 2% percent of the total population, and remains on the rise. They are coming to the realization that, to paraphrase the witty lines from the critically acclaimed by musical Avenue Q, *"Everyone is a little bit racist."*

Figure: American perspective towards Japan in World War II:

Source: IZANAU.COM, 2018

Surely, homogeneity of Japan is a false narrative, and just like other nations, Japan has a dark history of suppressing indigenous people including the Burakumin, the Ryukyuan, and the Ainu in Hokkaido, who technically make up largest minority of Japan based on ethnicity but are still not recognized that much (ethnically similar but treated and known as lowest caste in society). Following World War II, the majority of the Chinese and Korean immigrants who stayed in Japan after the war did not do any better. The Japan NGO Network for the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (ERD Net) published the 'Joint Civil Society Report on Racial Discrimination' in Japan recently, detailing contemporary and historical records of discrimination faced by minorities focusing on the Koreans living in Japan identified as Zainichi Koreans after World War II. The study has a somber tone. This report gives the idea that this wouldn't be unreasonable to conclude that Japan seems to be on track of South Africa's apartheid system. Perhaps some background is important.

Japan has historically benefited from the "sameness myth," managing to alternate between second and the third biggest economy in the world since nineties despite the destruction the nation found itself in in 1945. It must be emphasized again and again that Japan accomplished this without the aid of any natural resources, rather through unwavering belief inside a unifying objective and the resulting hard work. Therefore, this might be difficult for the generation that committed its life to Japan Inc. to understand the benefits of diversity for the future of their nation; this may lead to xenophobia as well as opposition to reform. Human rights activists are regularly urging legislators for enacting anti-racism and anti-discrimination laws and as well as to gather detailed information on disadvantages faced by foreign immigrants. The administration didn't make any small efforts toward implementing these proposals until 2016. First initiative was taken by introducing a law "promoting efforts to eliminate discriminatory speech," that basically says that discriminatory speech should be eliminated without specifying how or what needs to be done. Second initiative was, conducting a Foreign Residents Survey that was constructed by Japan's Ministry of Justice and asked immigrants about their experiences with systemic racism. Despite the fact that the study's methodologies and findings are debatable, it included 4,252 respondents from 37 locations

and offers a limited window in to the first stories behind the mistreatment that immigrants in Japan sometimes experience.

The following is a list of talking points that have been widely circulated on the internet and in different media: Within the last five years, 39.3% of foreigners who sought new residency reported experiencing discrimination of some type, including 25% at work or school and around 33% of insulting *Zainichi* Koreans were put into the category with other foreign nationals in that survey, as well as their social and historical situation is delicate and complex in comparison to the engineers from Bangalore and graduate student from Bangkok. This is just one of many important caveats to the data, but it is also the most obvious. The survey's main finding was that prejudice occurs, as it does everywhere else. More information is needed, and the Japanese government can no longer claim ignorance.

In reaction to this study, the YouTube channel Asian Boss interviewed random foreigners on the streets of Tokyo about their individual experiences. Although anecdotal, their comments were far less tenuous. After being denied admittance into a bar, a guy from Fiji upheld his belief about Japanese people as more ignorant than to identify them as racists and that discriminatory behaviors are "ninja-like" rather than violent. Another respondent, an American of South Asian descent, made the observation that, more often than not, exposure to racism rather than inborn prejudice can dispel apprehension on the part of the Japanese person. Examples of these associations and credentials include the organization where you work for instance or even your proficiency in Japanese language. Japanese citizens were then questioned by Asian Boss about their opinions on Abe's proposal to import a significant number of non-Japanese workers for filling the vacancies in job market. Despite the participants' doubts about immigrants' capability to adapt Japanese culture, the majority agreed, Japan would need to be more globally integrated. Besides, allowing immigrants to work and live there would improve both the nation and the psyche of its citizens. Asian Boss questioned residents of Osaka about their perceptions of persons from China and Korea in a separate interview. The young people questioned perceptively noted the contrast in their ideas from their parents' and grandparents' views, which is fascinating given the harsh aspects of the past history in Japan with their East Asian neighbors are largely covered negatively in the text books. They criticized the media for spreading ugly caricatures on both sides. But while they made friendship with somebody from the two nations, they focused on the person keeping the historical drama aside. The ultra-right-wing fascist organization opposing *Zainichi* Koreans, known as the often holds protests against them against this background of progressive young people and maintains a sizable internet presence. However, individuals are retaliating. A *Zaitokukai* demonstration in Kobe, a western city, was encircled by anti-hate speech demonstrators who demanded a nation's freedom of racism. The demonstration had just 30 participants and a police blockage three times its size. This video reveals an aggressive aspect of Japanese people battling for their beliefs. State municipalities have used the 'Anti-Hate Speech Act' to penalize the *Zaitokukai* for their cruel behavior towards *Zainichi* Koreans.

The experiences of a nation are not determined by the actions of a select few. Though there is now little doubt that calmer heads are in control, historical conceptions of Japanism, anxiety, an absence of exposure as well as unfavorable perceptions spread by someone with loudest voice are causing waves in Japan. As more and more individuals enter Japan, the ordinary Japanese person's heart and mentality are changing. Oussouby Sacko, 16 years old Mali's native becoming naturalized Japanese citizen, became the first African-born President of a Japanese university at Kyoto's Seika University. He undoubtedly has his own ideas about how to modernize and globalize his institution, ideas that will certainly have a positive influence on future generations of Japanese people. Thus, the nation is moving towards the right way. Japanese people, according to research by psychologist Kazuo Mori of Matsumoto University, exhibit an unconscious prejudice towards black people and a preference for white people, which he attributes to how the media portrays them. "Imported American television shows and Hollywood movies from the US may have contributed to the comparable racial sentiments of Japanese people regarding black people in Japanese society." If this is the case, however, Western media has failed to explain to the Japanese what Westerners consider to be "racist." An example from recent history is the blackface issue that arose after Masatoshi Hamada, a well-known comedian, copied Eddie Murphy's role in "Beverly Hills Cop." In truth, Blackface has already been seen in less well-known theater shows in Japan.

A young college student named Takashii wanders about Tokyo and strikes up conversations with odd persons he encounters. His YouTube channel is jam-packed with a variety of open, man-on-the-street interviews that are often centered on a single social issue and typically start with the query "What's it like...?" The aspiring journalist recently questioned residents of America, Africa, and Jamaica about what it's like to be Black in Japan. One of the nations with the highest racial harmony is Japan. How might being an even smaller minority effect quality of life, given that racism is still a major problem in more diverse countries? The first lady, an African American who had spent six years in Japan teaching academic English, said, "When I first got here, I felt like a spectacle. She did, however, add, "I simply feel like I would live anyplace else... People will just glance because of their preconceived notions about Black people. The young lady was then questioned about her thoughts on young teens with dreadlocks in their hair. Some claim that it is appropriation, while others claim that it is appreciation. I don't like it personally, but I can't force anybody to do anything, she retorted. According to another African American who has been in Japan since 2016, "In America they admire Black people as a culture, not as a people. Here, it's similar in some ways. Two Kenyan ladies, however, had a different perspective. "I find the Japanese to be quite hospitable. Even the looks you get are not nasty. People just want to know. And everyone is kind. I've been assisted by Japanese strangers in so many instances, one person said. The first thing that springs to mind when meeting a Black African is "the national parks and animals," she did add, but Japanese people tend to "relate more" to Black Americans since they like their music and movies. The last interviewee, a Jamaican guy, traveled to Japan to leave his native country and broaden his perspective on the globe. He said, "Thank God, Japanese people are not blatantly prejudiced, since a lot of the time I forget what color I am." He also made light of the fact that some of the most prevalent "positive preconceptions" about Black people seemed

to be true about him. They believe I can play basketball, sing well, or possess other super star traits. Japanese people regard you more like one of them the more you connect with them and join their social circle, he said.

In many respects, our world is becoming more open. We may be able to better understand how to create a more inclusive society by having more discussions similar to this. Baye McNeil, a Japanese citizen of American descent, attracted considerable attention online for his scathing condemnation of blackface. McNeil took pains to control his rage and control his animosity for the Japanese people. A college student who said: "As you surely know, the Japanese are not racist towards black people per se but are extremely uneducated about racial matters, was one of the intelligent responses he received from five individuals. However, as you said on Twitter, ignorance is not a defense. Similar to how black people prefer to recognize racism as "cultural ignorance" but not as a danger, the BBC's report on "being black in Japan" made this observation. In comparison to industrialized Western nations, Japan has exceptionally low crime rates, and numerous people interviewed indicated they felt safe from racist police harassment and assault.

The effects of this "cultural blindness" should not be discounted. We can only hope that occurrences like Mr. Hamada's blackface impersonation, which went viral on Twitter, will raise awareness across Japan. The ethnic groups closest to the Japanese, however, may merit the greatest consideration. The bulk of replies to the government's poll on racism were from ethnically Korean and Chinese individuals, who had been assimilating into Japanese culture long before Westerners. These individuals are known as "*Zainichi*" in Japan, which means "those who dwell in Japan," despite the fact that many of them are native Japanese, question arises how many of them would be ready to voice their concerns in a society that values patience and perseverance.

8.7 Racism during Covid 19

The global Covid-19 challenge, which began in 2020, has had a variety of effects upon Japanese society. This crisis reduced the influence of the left-leaning parties in Japan. Across the other side, right-wing opposition forces and far-right groups had grown in influence. The condition results in extremely severe persecution of socially weak, ethnic minorities, and sexual minorities. Additionally, far-right groups support the oppression of Jews. Racism is surfacing or becoming more pronounced, particularly in the wake of the Covid-19 dispute, which insisted on treating foreigners residing in Japan, like Chinese and Koreans, in a similar manner as Jews. A law that forbids racial discrimination exists in Japan. But there are no legal sanctions included. Ethnic minorities residing in Japan face danger from incomplete laws. Racist assaults against individuals of various races or ethnicities had increased after Covid-19's sixth wave in Japan. And the common Japanese had caught the exclusive hostility bug. The biggest Chinatown in Japan, Yokohama, received notes informing many eateries spreading hate comments towards Chinese and called them garbage and told to leave Japan soon. Numerous protest appealed urging not to spend taxes for foreigners and to keep them out of hospitals (BBC, 2021) . As saults on Koreans in Japan (Japanese-Korean), who had historically been the focus of the worst discriminatory acts,

were similarly severe. The paradox had been aimed at Korean children and women each time Japan and Korea (North/South Korea) had deteriorating relationship. The public authority began to indicate that entertainment and leisure venues were the primary source of Corona infection after sixth wave. Following the release of the gov't's report, racial assaults were launched against the mostly Korean-Japanese-run entertainment centers (The Hindu, 2021) . Today's discrimination towards immigrants in Japan is a result of intentional systematic racism. Since around 100 years ago, racism had been institutionalized by the government. Even during, Covid-19, the major perpetrators of the assault were regular Japanese people who were motivated by official propaganda. Even now, Japanese-Koreans continue to worry regarding and often discuss the Japanese massacres that occurred during earthquakes in 1923. Each time a natural disaster strikes, Japanese social networking sites (SNS) are inundated with postings labeling foreigners "dangerous" and encouraging "violence ". And the Covid-19 problem was not different. The second ethnic Korean-Japanese school in Japan, which opened shortly after World War II, was shut down in March, 2022. The primary educational institution that protected educational rights for ethnic minorities residing in Japan was demolished by racism intensified under Covid-19. The struggle between the Koreans and the Japanese, who are deliberately split, is also quite severe. Additionally, Koreans with extremely little financial resources formed nearly entirely the united front campaign opposing racism. People in Japan have a pressing responsibility to combat racism and eradicate xenophobic stereotypes. The lengthy past of political and racial oppression is still reflected in a perilous precursor to repressions. In December 2021, a racist set fire to a neighborhood in Kyoto with a Korean population as though in retaliation for the incitement of violence. And five buildings were destroyed by fire. The defendant had been accused with arson and targeting Japanese-Koreans. This was a simple example of side-effect of spreading racial hatreds during Covid-19 (Craig, 2022).

9. Conclusion:

In spite of the fact that the Japanese government denies the existence of racism, racism may be found in Japan. The Japanese Constitution provides a definition of race, but the people who have been victimized by racism in Japan do not meet that description. This is the rationale for the denial. In contrast, when seen through the lens of a more comprehensive definition of "race," groups like the Ainu and the Buraku people are examples of races that are regarded as having a distinct ancestral history. And the term "racism" refers to the practice of discriminating against these individuals. It is imperative that prompt action be taken to remedy the situation in which the majority of people as well as the government continue to deny the existence of racism. The term "Nihonjinron" is often regarded as the root of these racist attitudes. This concept of the racial and cultural homogeneity of Japan existed throughout the pre-war era of Japan. It manifested itself as a version of the emperor system that was founded on mythology, as well as the group-oriented and collectivistic part of the culture of Japan. Even before they began to adopt the idea of a nation-state, there was already a clear separation between "Japanese" and "others" in their society.

Beginning in 1868 and continuing during the Meiji Restoration, the idea of the country was also beginning to take shape. In addition, in order to defend themselves against an attack, they gained fresh expertise from the nations of Europe. They were making every effort to safeguard the nation. As a direct consequence of this, a novel concept of race was formed that was predicated on observable physical characteristics. This concept, along with eugenics and scientific racism, was established with the intention of demonstrating that the Japanese race was superior to other races. Based on their learning, an individual Japanese was recognized into 'yellow' race category; nevertheless, people rejected the notion that they belonged in this group and established "Nihonjinron." They placed a strong emphasis on distinguishing themselves from other Asian groups and the value of Japan's race, both of which contributed to the rise of imperialism during that time period. It fostered the racist notion that one race was inherently superior to another, which led to the conquest of other Asian countries and the slaughter of their inhabitants. However, it continued to be known as "Nihonjinron" after the end of imperialism in 1945, when nationalism began to decline at the same time. In the latter half of the 20th century, there were factions of "new nationalism" that emphasized on Japan's inherent unity, which was centered on either the emperor or Shido. It is very clear that "Nihonjinron" is the primary contributor to racism in Japan, as well as the primary reason why the Japanese government denies the existence of racism. Discrimination against persons of "mixed blood" is, as a result, often overlooked or disregarded. Having said that, the issue is a serious one. They are mostly discriminated against due to the fact that they have a foreign appearance and are regarded as such. In addition to this, they are often the target of bullying or other unpleasant treatment due to unfavorable preconceptions or attributions that are directed towards them as "others." To be able to call oneself Japanese requires navigating a path that is quite congested. They have to be of the "Japanese race," have a Japanese parent, be familiar with the culture, seem to be Japanese, and meet a number of other requirements. On the other hand, due to the fact that the term "Japanese" has a hazy meaning in context of Japanese concept, there is no one who can definitively explain the meaning of being Japanese or the requirements one must fulfill. Individual's perception of who they are must thus determine their identity. People are not permitted to call themselves "Japanese" as long as "Nihonjinron" and its persecution remain in place. Therefore, "Nihonjinron" is a notion that is really contributing to the development of racism in Japan. The myth persisted throughout Japanese history and continues to have a bearing on the Japanese people's conception of race and identity, as well as their unfavorable attitudes toward outsiders. Without a grasp of this principle, all attempts made in order to reform rules or advance the anti-discrimination movement would have been doomed to failure. This is necessary not only for the Japanese government but also for the Japanese people to adopt the understanding that this is a "myth" that has been socially and historically formed owing to the need in the past to unify and control the nation. In addition to this, they have to fight the preconceived notions that others have about them.

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